

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF ETHNOCULTURAL IDENTITY OF YOUTH THROUGH MUSICAL FOLKLORE

Bizhanova K.

Arinova B.

Al- Farabi Kazakh National university

Department of Pedagogy and Educational management.

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Global changes in society, ongoing fundamental socio-economic reforms have a significant impact on the process of socialization of the individual, the formation of the younger generation. While the individual has long been considered an object of education, today he is developing as a self-organizing and self-improving subject.

Features of virtual communication, social isolation, difficulties associated with stress and depression, psychological instability, the increase in harmful habits, a multicultural environment, the influence of mass media on the education of youth, and the role of pop culture, social media and advertising require special attention to the education of youth. These changes taking place in society have a negative impact on the preservation of values, the education of youth, and our national traditions. This is because a significant wrong stereotype is being formed among young people, due to their outlook on life. Today, such various topical issues that occur in the lives of young people are, in fact, the problems of the entire society.

Therefore, the strategic direction of the socialization of the individual in our country is aimed at the formation of new people who think in a new and creative way, with a developed culture. Today, the requirements for education and personal development, in line with socio-cultural changes, require special attention to the spiritual development and education of young people, who are the future of the nation.

In this regard, the analysis of current factors affecting young people is a source of knowledge of ethnocultural identity for representatives of the young community, who are aimed at learning the history of their country, respecting their language, and increasing their love for their country. In particular, the role of folklore in the education of youth is enormous. This is because through folklore we can form a national-cultural and ethnic mentality in young people, as well as increase emotional-moral and good qualities in a person. Nowadays, folklore is a rarely used musical genre. However, folklore is not only a musical genre, but also a national value that is inextricably linked with our nation.

"The Kazakhs are a people rich in proverbs and sayings, which have been carefully selected over the centuries, through the refinement of national thought and consciousness. This is a rich source of wealth for folk poets who equally hold the reins of oral and written literature. From the poetry of poets-zhyrau to classical literature that stands shoulder to shoulder with modern world literature, you will not find a jewel of words that

is not inspired by oral literature." [2] Therefore, the thought underlying the words indicates the importance of the rich national treasure in the education of young people.

Uniqueness is an important phenomenon that allows people to identify the social group to which they belong or to define themselves individually. The concept of uniqueness is also widely used in social sciences in analyzing the relationship of social changes and in determining the strategy of self-knowledge or self-identity.

For this reason, the socialization of an individual, participation in group cooperation, self-searching and knowing what he is are born from the natural need to understand the reason for his existence. This is because music, as one of the most influential means of culture, strengthens the bond between generations and allows preserving national values.

Musical folklore is a reflection of the life and worldview of our ancestors. It is passed down from generation to generation, expressing historical events and our way of life, and folklore expresses our national identity. If the musical heritage is preserved, national consciousness and cultural identity are preserved. In the process of studying musical folklore, we notice its great impact on the spiritual development and creative growth of young people, its great importance in the upbringing of generations. Through musical folklore, young people feel spiritual harmony, and through musical folklore, they establish relationships with representatives of other cultures, and understanding and friendship between ethnic groups are formed. Therefore, musical folklore is one of the spiritual values that are passed down from generation to generation. It imbues young people with national values and creates conditions for the formation of cultural consciousness. The historical weight and meaning of songs and kyui enrich the spiritual world of young people, show the continuity of the past and present of the nation. Folklore reflects the spiritual wealth of the nation, can be an important tool in educating patriotic and patriotic young people.

To do this, the following steps must be taken.

These steps:

Offer educational programs about musical folklore.

Frequent promotion of national cultural events.

Actively involve and support young people in the promotion of national values.

Musical folklore gives a new impetus to the education and development of young people. All efforts

should be directed to the preservation and modernization of national culture. Educating the younger generation as cultured, humane, creative individuals who master the history, origin, customs, traditions, language, and knowledge of their people is the law of life, the demand of society. This law creates the need to familiarize young people with the national treasure, its national culture, customs, and traditions in a deeper way. "Its selected examples, inherited from generation to generation, are an indispensable tool for educating the younger generation. The only source of the foundations for forming and developing national values in students is traditional Kazakh music." [3] In musical folklore, there is a lot of our ancient heritage, characterized by many thematically relevant, artistic and genre features that have developed from national psychology. They are from the moment a person is born (lullabies), the essence of the entire moral life is formed as a national code, and continues until the eternal period (death poems). Kazakh songs and kuys have a special place in the path of reviving the spirit of the nation. Because our precious heritage, preserved from ancient times, contains wonderful pearls of folk wisdom.

That is why we believe that modern research should take into account the pedagogical issues of shaping future youth and future personalities. Because the role of musical education in shaping a personality is very high. Being educated is a manifestation of our own identity and development. The development of a personality encourages us to strive forward and stand out from the crowd. Through education, a person learns how to interact with others. An individual in the process of his character shows his personal qualities, views, and psychological appearance. Through personality traits, a person not only expresses his worldview and aspirations, but also stands out for his personal growth. The behavior of a person who is endowed with national values innately causes respect for them in society. Rude behavior can destroy the personality of any person. In the education system, people learn the rules of behavior on how to behave with others. This is because the actions of a person, which are reflected in society, are a specific set of his rules of behavior. Therefore, national education contributes to the formation of young people as full-fledged individuals.

Social media, the Internet play an important role in the lives of young people. Young people can easily share any information, exchange their thoughts, and they can find new friends through social networks. This shows that communication in the virtual space, in line with the changing times, has an impact on the upbringing of young people. In addition, online communication skills can be developed and cooperation can be established, but at the same time, a decrease in the ability to communicate in person can lead to social isolation, loneliness and depression, decreased self-confidence, and weakened interpersonal skills.

"The second process that is currently underway is globalization. In order not to fall into the trap of globalization, we must be able to properly preserve our spiritual heritage, national songs and heritage from the very beginning. However, mere preservation is not enough...

It is necessary to be able to use that heritage in accordance with today's trends, requirements, and tastes, while preserving its national character." [4]

The following opinion continues that the task of socio-cultural activity is to develop the education of young people based on ethnocultural values. "The history, oral literature, ethnic symbols, customs, traditions, spiritual and moral values of each people are reflected and form the best values and qualities to this day." [5]. The national idea of the Eternal Nation emphasizes that it is possible to cherish one's language, customs, and traditions only by preserving the socio-cultural code of the life experience of the Kazakh people. [6].

Through the art of music, historical melodies, epic poems, and life customs that are passed down from father to son, we can shape our national identity and educate the youth and the rising generation. In this context, the research of scientists is also valuable: "... Through cultural creative activity, one can understand the thinking patterns and intellectual development of peoples, their ability to adapt to life." [7].

In short, at all times our people have paid special attention to the education of their future - youth. Now all the efforts of society should be directed to the education of the younger generation in patriotism, morality, and humanity. A well-educated, educated, conscious, and cultured generation is a strong pillar of the state. The rational use of the centuries-old traditions of patriotic education and national traditions of our people in the formation of youth is the need of the hour.

Cultural influences and conformity in the upbringing of youth in society affect the formation, development, and upbringing of the personality of modern youth in a multicultural environment with different cultural environments. Cultural contact, interaction with different cultures in other environments, influence young people to be tolerant and respect different cultural traditions. A multicultural environment contributes to enriching their personal experience and forming a global experience, forming a worldview. However, national values are of great importance in the upbringing of young people. Folk music is closely related to the history of mankind. National music reflects the courage, courage, and honor of our people, the way of life of the nation. Musical folklore, passed down from generation to generation, is the basis of national education.

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